

Original Article

Semi-automated reproducible target transfer for cardiac radioablation – A multi-center cross-validation study within the RAVENTA trial

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Ventricular tachycardia
STAR
Stereotactic Arrhythmia Radioablation
Target volume definition
Target transfer
Semi-automated software solutions
Quality assurance
Cross-validation
CARDIO-RT
EAMapReader
RAVENTA

ABSTRACT

Background: Stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation (STAR) is a therapeutic option for ventricular tachycardia (VT) where catheter-based ablation is not feasible or has previously failed. Target definition and its transfer from electro-anatomic maps (EAM) to radiotherapy treatment planning systems (TPS) is challenging and operator-dependent. Software solutions have been developed to register EAM with cardiac CT and semi-automatically transfer 2D target surface data into 3D CT volume coordinates. Results of a cross-validation study of two conceptually different software solutions using data from the RAVENTA trial (NCT03867747) are reported.

Methods: Clinical Target Volumes (CTVs) were created from target regions delineated on EAM using two conceptually different approaches by separate investigators on data of 10 patients, blinded to each other's results. Targets were transferred using 3D-3D registration and 2D-3D registration, respectively. The resulting CTVs were compared in a core-lab using two complementary analysis software packages for structure similarity and geometric characteristics.

Results: Volumes and surface areas of the CTVs created by both methods were comparable: 14.88 ± 11.72 ml versus 15.15 ± 11.35 ml and 44.29 ± 33.63 cm² versus 46.43 ± 35.13 cm². The DICE-coefficient was 0.84 ± 0.04 ; median surface-distance and HAUSDORFF-distance were 0.53 ± 0.37 mm and 6.91 ± 2.26 mm, respectively. The 3D-center-of-mass difference was 3.62 ± 0.99 mm. Geometrical volume similarity was 0.94 ± 0.05 %.

Conclusion: The STAR targets transferred from EAM to TPS using both software solutions resulted in nearly identical 3D structures. Both solutions can be used for QA (quality assurance) and EAM-to-TPS transfer of STAR-

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targets. Semi-automated methods could potentially help to avoid mistargeting in STAR and offer standardized workflows for methodically harmonized treatments.

Background

Ventricular tachycardia (VT) is a leading cause of mortality in patients with structural heart disease.[1,2] Implantable cardioverter-defibrillator (ICD) therapy can prevent sudden cardiac death but does not prevent recurrent arrhythmia, which is usually addressed through antiarrhythmic drugs and/or catheter ablation of the arrhythmogenic substrate.[1,3] Stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation (STAR) with a single fraction of 25 Gy has been proposed as a bail-out strategy in patients not suitable for catheter ablation or refractory to this therapy.[4–7].

Defining the three-dimensional (3D) target in the radiotherapy treatment planning systems (TPS) presents unique challenges. Whereas usual radiotherapy targets are readily identifiable, the arrhythmogenic substrate is primarily defined by its electrophysiological properties which are mostly established through an electrophysiological study (EPS) using 3D electro-anatomic mapping (EAM).[8] Free-hand delineation of the target region as defined on EAM (2D surface) in the TPS on treatment planning computed tomography (CT) shows poor interobserver consistency even when performed by experienced electrophysiologists/radiation oncologists.[9] Furthermore, clinically relevant errors have been reported with such free-hand “eyeballing” methods.[10].

To address the need for improved transfer methods and quality assurance (QA), several software solutions have been developed which register EAM with contrast enhanced ECG-triggered cardiac CT, (CECT) and allow for the 2D target definition on the EAM data to be semi-automatically transferred into the 3D CT coordinates.[11–15]

Although these workflows have been used for QA in multi-center trials [16,17], direct clinical validation has been hampered by the lack of established gold standards. Since manual target transfer is prone to significant interobserver variation[9] and thus unsuitable as a ground truth, we report the cross-validation results of two novel, conceptually different in-house developed software solutions[11,14] for target transfer QA in STAR using clinical data from centers participating in the RAVENTA trial (NCT03867747).

Methods

Study design

We aimed to compare the results of two novel, conceptually different, in-house developed semi-automated software solutions [11,14] to transfer 2D target surface regions defined in EAM space to a 3D clinical target volume (CTV) defined on contrast enhanced ECG-triggered cardiac CT in the radiotherapy TPS. Both target transfer approaches have been published previously[11,14] and are described in detail below. The target transfer using both methods was performed by separate investigators, blinded to each other’s results. The resulting CTVs were compared by a third investigator in a core lab using two complementary software packages (Velocity, Varian, Palo Alto, CA, USA and Admire, Elekta, Stockholm, Sweden). (Fig. 1).

Dataset acquisition and preparation

Patients underwent STAR within a prospective trial (RAVENTA)[16]

Fig. 1. Study design and analysis workflow. See text for details.

or as compassionate use following consensus guidelines.[4,18] Pseudonymized data was collected from the treating centers. Ethics approval was obtained for the coordinating center (reference-number D555/18) and each local site and/or for STAR benchmark studies (D476/19 and D483/21). Informed consent to pseudonymized data sharing was obtained before treatment.

ECG-gated contrast-enhanced cardiac CTs (CECT) per local protocol were acquired as part of treatment planning. The CECT used was the scanner-determined “best diastolic” volume. This corresponds well to the EAM, which acquires point locations during diastole. EAMs were created either during VT ablation attempts or as dedicated procedure for STAR. The EAM-systems used were at the discretion of the treating center (Carto v7, Biosense Webster, Diamond Bar, CA, USA; Ensite NavX, Abbott Laboratories, Abbott Park, IL, USA; Rhythmia HDx, Boston Scientific, Marlborough, MA, USA).

Screenshots were taken on the EAM workstation. For the 2D-3D approach, standard projections such as anterior-posterior or strictly lateral were obtained, whereas for the 3D-3D approach, any angulation with a good view of the target region (standard projections or oblique views) was used. In addition, the native EAM data was exported in the respective proprietary file format. The target on the EAM screenshot was marked by the treating cardiac electrophysiologist and was used as a given input for both approaches.

For each patient case, cardiac structures such as the contrast-filled LV blood-pool, the right ventricular cavity, the aorta and the LV myocardium[5] were segmented from the CECT by the local cardiologist or the radiation oncologist and were exported as DICOM radiotherapy structure sets (RTSS). This radiotherapy structure set and the CECT, both in DICOM format, the screenshots with the delineated targets (JPEG format), and the exported EAM data (vendor-proprietary file format) were used as common input for both registration methods. The transfer using each method was performed by an experienced team (electrophysiologist/cardiologist; radiation oncologist; medical physicist; engineer).

Semi-automated target surface transfer for CTV creation

Three-dimensional registration: 3D Slicer and EAMapReader

Three-dimensional (3D-3D) registration was performed using the open-source 3D Slicer software for medical image analysis (version 5.0.3, 3D Slicer contributors, <https://www.slicer.org/>) and the EAMapReader extension.[11,19] In brief, the 3D EAM was registered to the (endocardial) structure of the LV as contoured on the CECT (slice-thickness 0.8–1 mm) using a manual alignment followed by an *iterative closest-point* optimization of the distance between both structures, resulting in a rigid (6-degrees-of-freedom) 3D transformation. Where available, EAM of the aorta or the right ventricle were used as additional landmarks to reduce rotational ambiguity and increase overall robustness.

The registration of the EAM to the CECT results in a 4x4 transformation matrix which can be decomposed into sequential rotations around the principal axes. Rotation (Euler) angles around the left–right, anterior-posterior, and inferior-superior axes were calculated from the final registration matrix.

After registration, a target structure was contoured directly onto the EAM in 3D Slicer to re-create the target surface delineated on the corresponding EAM screenshots. Since the arrhythmogenic substrate can be located at any depth within the ventricular wall, and because catheter ablation failure is often due to inaccessible substrate deep in the LV myocardium, a transmural target volume is generally used for STAR. Accordingly, in order to create a transmural target volume from the endocardial target surface on the EAM, it is necessary to add LV wall thickness to create a 3D target volume. This was done by adding the full myocardial thickness (defined at the time of segmentation through thresholding and grow-from-seed algorithms) subtended by the target surface. The resulting target structure was smoothed with a Gaussian

smoothing kernel with a 3 mm width according the CT slice thickness identically in both workflows. (Fig. 2).

Two-dimensional registration: CARDIO-RT

Two-dimensional (2D-3D) registration was performed using the CARDIO-RT software (Institute for Robotics and Cognitive Systems of the University of Lübeck, Germany) which is available upon request.[14] The MATLAB-based application (The MathWorks Inc, MA, USA) enables registration of CT volumes of the respective cardiac chamber with standardized screenshots of the corresponding EAM. Screenshots of the electroanatomic map with the marked target region were loaded into CARDIO-RT, along with the RTSS segmentations of the LV blood pool and other cardiac substructures from the contrast enhanced cardiac CT. (Fig. 3) The screenshots were overlaid onto a corresponding projection of the CT segmentations and the segmentation was shifted (translated) and rotated to obtain an optimal match to the screenshot image. The translation offsets and rotation angles were saved for later analysis. Once this registration had been finalized, the marked target region on the screenshot was delineated on the registered segmentation, resulting in a point cloud on the segmentation surface.

These selected points were then saved into the original RTSS file and this 2D structure was transformed into a 3D CTV in the cardiac CT space by extending it transmurally across the LV myocardium and smoothed with a 3 mm radius, as described above.

Structure analysis, evaluation and statistical analysis

The resulting 3D CTVs generated independently by the blinded investigators using both methods were transferred to a core lab and imported into commercial software for dedicated 3D-structure analysis (Velocity, V3.2.1, Varian Inc., Palo Alto, USA). We analyzed and compared structure characteristics for overlap and similarity: structure volumes, surface areas, distances and differences between the 3D centers-of-mass (3D-CoM), conformity index (SØRENSEN-DICE coefficient, range 0–1), geometric structure similarity (independently of overlap), and surface distance metrics (median surface distance and HAUSDORFF distance [HD]). Whereas the median surface distance is the median distance of nearest-neighbor pairs of points from both structures, the HD is the maximum distance of the two structures. In addition, we evaluated sensitivity (SEN, proportion of identical voxels) and specificity (SPEC).[9,20] A second dedicated research software solution (ADMIRE, V3.47, Elekta, Stockholm, Sweden) was used to independently validate the results and analyze additional parameters of structure agreement, as reported previously.[20].

Continuous variables were compared and differences were evaluated using the *t*-test or the Mann-Whitney test, as appropriate. It should be noted that the number of cases lacks the power to identify *statistical* significance in minor differences. However, descriptive statistics allow for the evaluation whether the magnitude of observed differences is of *clinical* significance. Values are given as mean \pm standard deviation unless noted otherwise. Statistical analysis was performed using R 4.0.5 and RStudio 1.3 (Posit Software, Boston, MA, USA).

Results

Detailed patient characteristics are summarized in Suppl. Table 1. All 10 patients have been treated with a single dose of 25 Gy prescribed to the surrounding isodose surface while adhering to critical structure constraints according to the RAVENTA trial-protocol.[16] Data regarding baseline demographics, STAR planning and delivery, and initial clinical follow-up have previously been reported for some of these patients.[17,21,22].

In 10 patients, complete datasets were obtained and registration using both approaches was successfully completed. For six patients, EAM of the (thoracic) aorta was available and used in combination with the LV for registration with the respective structures on the CECT. For

Fig. 2. Representative case of 3D-3D registration followed by target creation using 3D Slicer 5.0.3 and the EAMapReader extension: (A) Contouring of relevant cardiac structures. LV cavity, magenta; aorta, light blue; LV myocardium, brown. (B) 3D representation of the segmentation and geometry of the electroanatomic (EA) map (yellow). (C, D) 3D rendering (C) and short-axis reformation (D) of the EAM (LV and aorta) after rigid registration with the segmentation. (E) Side-by-side view of the imported EAM in 3D Slicer (left) and the corresponding screenshot from the mapping workstation (right) (Carto, Biosense Webster). The white design line in the mapping screenshot (right) denotes the intended target. Note the corresponding contouring in progress (red) on the imported model (left). (F, G) resulting transmural CTV (green). While (A)-(G) show a case using the Carto3 mapping system, other mapping systems lead to similar results: (H) corresponding step to panel (E) in a case using Rhythmia HDx. (I) corresponding step to panel (E) in a case using Ensight NavX. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the remaining four cases, other landmarks such as partial EAM of the right ventricular outflow tract or the endocardial impressions of the left ventricular papillary muscles were used to reduce rotational ambiguity around the LV long axis.

All cases resulted in comparable, very similar 3D CTVs regarding size or anatomical position (Figs. 4, 5). The volumes and surface areas of the CTV-structures were comparable and without significant differences: 14.88 ± 11.72 ml versus 15.15 ± 11.35 ml ($p = 0.54$) and 44.29 ± 33.63 cm² versus 46.43 ± 35.13 cm² ($p = 0.18$), for 3D-3D and 2D-3D registrations, respectively. The mean difference in volumes and surface areas were 0.37 ± 1.81 ml and 2.14 ± 4.67 cm², respectively. Comparing both structures, the DICE coefficient was 0.84 ± 0.04 with sensitivity of 0.86 ± 0.05 and specificity of 0.96 ± 0.02 . The median surface distance between both structures was 0.53 ± 0.37 mm, and the HAUSDORFF distance 6.91 ± 2.26 mm. The distance between the 3D-centers-of-mass was 3.62 ± 0.99 mm and the geometrical volume similarity regardless of volume coordinates was 0.94 ± 0.05 . All variables which were available in both analysis software packages were identical. Detailed results are summarised in (Table 1).

For cases where neither aorta nor RV was available on the EAM, we expected to see greater differences in the CTVs due to rotational ambiguity and the conceptually different approach between the two registration methods. Indeed, we observed that the case with the lowest DICE

coefficient (0.76) had neither aorta nor RV in the EAM. However, no statistically significant differences in distances and similarity metrics were found when comparing the cases with additional aorta or RV EAM to those without.

The patient is positioned head-first-supine both during CT acquisition and during EAM. Differences in body posture (arms above the head for CT) and diaphragm position induce some rotation of the heart within the body, as do minor differences in patient positioning. To investigate the need to routinely account for rotation, we calculated the amount of rotation around the three principal patient axes for each case with both methods. As expected, amounts of rotation were similar for both methods, but ranged widely between cases from almost none up to more than 20° around two axes each (Suppl. Fig. 1).

Discussion

In this multi-center study, we cross-validated two conceptually different approaches to transfer an endocardial EAM-defined 2D target surface for STAR into the radiotherapy treatment planning systems. The main findings of the presented study are:

1. Both methods were technically feasible in all patient datasets across various EAM systems and local cardiac CT acquisition protocols.

Fig. 3. Representative case of 2D-3D registration followed by target creation using CARDIO-RT and 3D Slicer 5.0.3: (A) Carto EAM screenshot and the CT-based LV blood pool (red) and aorta (blue) used as additional registration fiducial before registration. The EAM screenshot and CT-based point clouds are both viewed from superior, and the white design line in the EAM screenshot denotes the intended target. (B) Registered EAM screenshot and CT-based contours. (C) Target points on the LV blood pool defined by delineated polygon along the intended target. (D) Target (red) on the CT slices and three-dimensional models of LV blood pool. (E) Transmural CTV (green) according to the CARDIO-RT output. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

2. The final 3D Clinical Target Volume (CTV) structures from both target transfer approaches showed excellent similarity metrics.
3. Due to the fundamentally different registration approaches (3D-3D vs. 2D-3D), we hypothesize that a systematic error is highly unlikely and each approach serves as *ground truth* for the other, cross-validating both.

Optimized target definition for STAR is essential to avoid VT recurrence, as this novel non-invasive treatment method is, contrary to the iterative approach of catheter-based ablation, a one-step procedure. Precisely delineated CTVs for irradiation are paramount to reduce radiation dose to healthy cardiac substructures and neighboring organs-at-risk and hence to avoid toxicity. However, target definition for STAR and its transfer to the TPS is a complex and multi-disciplinary process.

The first step, performed by cardiac electrophysiologists, consists of the definition of the critical target region in the left ventricle on the EAM. Generally, the goal is to define the critical isthmus of the reentry circuit or, less common, the focal origin of the arrhythmia.[1,3] It is considered standard of care to use 3D EAM systems to elucidate the arrhythmia substrate and mechanism.[8] However, the precise location and extent of the target for STAR is defined as a 2D surface (endo- or epicardial) on this 3D EAM. For the present technical cross-validation study, we considered the target surface region as a given input and studied methods to transfer the defined target from the EAM to the cardiac CT.

Initial reports of STAR[23–27] used anatomical landmarks (e.g. LV apex; aortic valve) or the American Heart Association (AHA) 17-segment model[28] as positional references to manually recreate the EAM-defined target region in the RT planning CT. Even the definition of the true LV apex on CT is far from intuitive[29], and such manual

approaches for the EAM-to-TPS target transfer have yielded poor inter-operator consistency. Even when performed by experienced clinicians, the resulting CTVs showed remarkable variability both in localization and extent with 3D-CoM differences up to 35 mm and D_{ICE} coefficients as low as 0.02.[9] Those differences can lead to clinically relevant problems, as demonstrated by targeting errors for STAR leading to missed substrate areas and VT recurrence.[10] To improve the target transfer robustness, semi-automated approaches were published to register the EAM to the cardiac CT with high accuracy.[11,13] Both workflows, as well as subsequent work[12,15,30], used the 3D geometry of the EAM to register it to a closed-surface representation of the respective cardiac chamber in the cardiac CT. The technical implementations differ slightly between those publications, mainly with respect to the range of usable 3D mapping data and, in some cases, the use of closed-source third-party software. Still, the core concept of 3D-3D registration is similar among all these workflows.

Validation efforts of these methods were hampered by the lack of baseline reference data, and since all implementations used a similar approach, common confounders inherent to the methods could not be ruled out. This changed with the development of the CARDIO-RT approach that uses a different paradigm, namely 2D-3D registration [14], which enabled the cross-validation of two independent transfer methods for the first time. The structure transfer by both approaches, feasible for different EAM systems and CT acquisition protocols, resulted in high agreement with near-identical CTV extent and localization with a median 3D-CoM difference of 3.6 mm and a median DICE coefficient of 0.84.

Fig. 4. Transversal, sagittal, and coronal views of a representative transferred transmural clinical target volume (CTV). A-C. CTV (green) by 3D-3D registration, D-F. CTV by 2D-3D registration (red), G-I. Overlay and visual comparison of both structures. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. A. EAM with marked VT target surface (white contour). B-D: 3D view of the CTV transferred by 2D-3D registration (red) and 3D-3D registration (green), and overlay of both structures. Magenta, LV blood pool; orange, coronary arteries; blue, aorta. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Clinical application

The present work supports that both 3D-3D registration as well as 2D-3D registration can be used to integrate the EAM of different vendors with CECT with high accuracy. Given the poor results obtained in benchmark studies of manual target transfer, we recommend using one of these computer-aided approaches for quality assurance in STAR. The use of a specific approach or software solution should be based on operator preference and institutional experience: While 2D-3D registration does not depend on exported mapping data (theoretically improving long-term stability of the approach, since mapping system vendors might change or discontinue export functionalities), 3D-3D

registration offers added flexibility (non-standard views showing the target region; integration of additional DICOM modalities). Both approaches could also be used in parallel for a cross-check of the results. Further studies in larger patient cohorts are needed to elucidate differences between transfer methods and predictors for improved registration.

Limitations

The results of the present study should be viewed in the light of the inherent limitations, the first of which is the modest sample size. We were able to use 10 data sets in the framework of a clinical trial protocol.

Table 1

Structure analysis results. Abbreviations: DICE, Sørensen-DICE-coefficient; 3D-CoM: 3-dimensional center of mass, CTV, clinical target volume. ° Cases with no additional map of the aorta/RV. *Mean difference of generated volumes -0.37 ml, 95 % confidence interval $[-1.66$ ml; 0.93 ml], p-value: 0.5366. ** Mean difference of generated surfaces -2.14 cm², 95 % confidence interval $[-5.48$ cm²; 1.20 cm²] p-value: 0.181.

Case	Volume (ml)*		Surface area (cm ²)**		Overlap/Similarity parameters						
	3D-3D	2D-3D	3D-3D	2D-3D	DICE	Median Surface distance (mm)	HAUSDORFF distance (mm)	3D-CoM difference (mm)	Volume Similarity	Sensitivity	Specificity
1	18.85	16.37	48.73	47.26	0.90	0.0	5.30	2.34	0.92	0.82	0.99
2	8.64	8.32	27.15	26.38	0.84	0.67	6.04	4.16	0.98	0.82	0.97
3°	2.18	2.47	10.28	10.05	0.84	0.63	4.87	1.44	0.94	0.89	0.96
4	31.77	33.01	76.13	72.94	0.88	0.68	7.39	2.91	0.98	0.90	0.96
5	40.72	39.11	130.47	138.33	0.78	0.79	11.55	4.62	0.98	0.77	0.98
6°	6.68	9.78	25.84	35.17	0.76	0.81	10.99	4.17	0.81	0.93	0.94
7°	15.42	18.56	47.37	55.93	0.83	0.0	8.12	4.23	0.91	0.92	0.96
8°	6.99	6.54	25.80	24.74	0.86	0.0	4.31	4.31	0.97	0.84	0.98
9	8.82	8.73	26.53	26.45	0.84	0.65	5.96	3.70	1.00	0.84	0.97
10	8.78	9.64	24.57	27.01	0.84	1.07	4.54	4.29	0.95	0.88	0.94
mean	14.88	15.25	44.29	46.43	0.84	0.53	6.91	3.62	0.94	0.86	0.96
SD	11.72	11.35	33.63	35.13	0.04	0.37	2.46	0.99	0.05	0.05	0.02

The limited number of cases precluded further analyses such as comparison of different mapping systems regarding registration accuracy or predictors for better agreement. Patient numbers are still limited for STAR and we were still able to use data sets for a wide range of mapping systems. Validation studies in larger cohorts, e.g., within the framework of the *Standardized Treatment and Outcome Platform for Stereotactic Therapy Of Re-entrant tachycardia by a Multidisciplinary (STOPSTORM) consortium*[5], or investigations of inter-operator variation for each approach are warranted.

While the spatial accuracy of magnetic-navigation EAM systems is impressive and an EPS is the only modality that can elucidate the electrophysiologic substrate, we acknowledge that there are other modalities to define putative arrhythmia substrates, such as cardiac MRI or CT scans. In this study, a rather recent map (not older than 4 weeks) was available for all cases. The used software (CARDIO-RT) also allow automated an AHA-segment based targeting. In the RAVENTA study, targeting was not segment based, to keep the CTVs small to avoid toxicities.

One should also be aware that the EAM-to-cardiac-CT transfer is not the only possible source of targeting errors: the cardiac CT has to be also registered to the non-contrast cardiac average planning CT. Direct registration of the EAM to the planning CT is not feasible for the lack of clear definition of the endocardial contour. The registration of the cardiac CT to the planning CT could thus induce further error. However, the registration of both CTs is usually aided by additional extracardiac structures and is usually quite robust.

Both approaches used investigational software solutions not yet approved for routine clinical use. However, given the experimental nature of STAR, these techniques may be used especially in clinical trials.

Conclusion

Using two conceptually different approaches for 2D target surface to 3D CTV transfer from EAM to cardiac CT we were able to show good agreement between both methods. Both techniques can thus be used for target transfer, quality assurance and analysis for STAR. (Semi-)Automated software solutions have the potential to reduce operator-dependent errors during radiotherapy treatment planning.

Sources of funding

The RAVENTA study is part of the EU-Horizon-2020 Standardized Treatment and Outcome Platform for Stereotactic Therapy Of Re-entrant tachycardia by a Multidisciplinary (STOPSTORM) consortium project (Grant Agreement Number 945119) and the participating centers in this

work have received funding for this project related to but not directly for the RAVENTA study.

Declaration of financial interests

S. Hohmann received travel grants from Boston Scientific Medizintechnik GmbH and speakers honoraria from Medtronic and Abbott, outside of the submitted work.

J. Boda-Heggemann: Speaker fees AstraZeneca GmbH, Research grant Elekta AB, consulting fees EBAMed SA outside the submitted work.

L. Kaestner: Speaker fee AstraZeneca GmbH outside the submitted work.

D. Buergy: Personal fees from NB Capital ApS, b.e. Imaging GmbH, and PharmaMar, all outside the submitted work.

D. Krug: DK has received honoraria from Merck Sharp & Dome, med update, onkowissen, best practice onkologie, ESO, ESMO, Gilead and Pfizer as well as research funding from Merck KGaA, outside the submitted work.

L.-H. Boldt: Honoraria from Biotronik, Boston Scientific, and Pfizer, outside of the submitted work.

F. A. Giordano: honoraria, research grants and/or travel support from Carl Zeiss Meditec AG, TME Pharma AG, Guerbet SA, Cureteq AG, Bristol-Myers Squibb, AstraZeneca GmbH, FoMF GmbH, MEDAC GmbH, Elsevier GmbH and stock/ownership from TME Pharma AG and Implacit GmbH.

D. Duncker received modest lecture honorary, travel grants and/or a fellowship grant from Abbott, Astra Zeneca, Biotronik, Boehringer Ingelheim, Boston Scientific, Bristol Myers Squibb, CVRx, Medtronic, Microport, Pfizer, Zoll.

O. Blanck is the section editor for medical physics of the *Strahlentherapie und Onkologie* journal.

N. Karfoul: Honoraria from Abbott outside of the submitted work.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Stephan Hohmann: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jingyang Xie:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Miriam Eckl:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Melanie Grehn:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration. **Nizar Karfoul:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Christian Janorschke:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Roland Merten:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Boris Rudic:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology,

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radonc.2024.110499>.

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